

Cyanoethylation of Nitroindoles

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4-, 5- and 6-Nitroindoles were subjected to cyanoethylation with acrylonitrile in presence of benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide to obtain the corresponding nitroindole-1-propionitriles. These nitriles on catalytic reduction with Raney nickel yielded the corresponding 1-(3-aminopropyl)aminoindoles. The nitriles were further hydrolysed to nitroindole-1-propionic acids. The nitroindole-1-propionitriles were also formylated to the respective 1-(2-cyanoethyl)nitroindole-3-aldehydes.

Various *Bz*-substituted indoles and their derivatives were subjected to cyanoethylation with acrylonitrile in presence of benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide (Triton B') to obtain the respective indole-1-propionitriles¹. It was established that the cyanoethyl group in presence of basic catalysts enters the 1-position of the indole nucleus. In continuation of this work, we now report the cyanoethylation of nitroindoles to get the respective nitroindole-1-propionitriles for the preparation of 1-(3-aminopropyl)aminoindoles and nitroindole-1-propionic acids.

During the present work, 4-, 5- and 6-nitroindoles, were subjected to cyanoethylation with acrylonitrile in presence of 'Triton B' to get the corresponding nitroindole-1-propionitriles (IIa-c) in 80% yield. 1-(3-Aminopropyl)aminoindoles (IIIa-c) were obtained in 60-70% yield, by the catalytic reduction of the above nitriles with Raney nickel. Nitroindole-1-propionitriles (IIa-c) were hydrolysed to yield the respective nitroindole-1-propionic acids (IVa-c) in 85-90% yield. Compounds (IIa-c) were formylated following the method of Smith² to obtain the corresponding 1-(2-cyanoethyl)-nitroindole-3-aldehydes (Va-c) in yields of about 60% to imply the fact that the position 3 in the cyanoethylindole must be free.

However, attempts to cyanoethylate 7-nitroindole under the above experimental conditions were unsuccessful probably due to the formation of hydrogen bonding between the nitro group at the position 7 and the N-H group of indole nucleus.

The IR spectra of the nitriles (IIa-c) showed peaks of moderate intensity at 2240 cm^{-1} characteristic of $\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ stretching vibrations. The spectra of compounds (IVa-c) showed strong peaks at 1709-1695 cm^{-1} characteristic of the $\text{C} = \text{O}$ stretching of carboxy group. The IR spectra of 1-(2-cyanoethyl) nitroindole-3-aldehydes (Va-c) showed a peak of moderate intensity at 2245-2240 cm^{-1} characteristic of $\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ stretching vibration and also showed a strong peak at 1660-1650 cm^{-1} corresponding to aldehyde carbonyl group. The absence of NH band in the above compounds was observed, thus providing proof that the cyanoethylation of nitroindoles in presence of base takes place at the 1-position and not at the 3-position of indole nucleus.

SCHEME

Ia-c	
IIa-c	a = -4-NO ₂
IVa-c	b = -5-NO ₂
Va-c	c = -6-NO ₂
IIIa-c	a = -4-NH ₂ , b = -5-NH ₂ , c = -β-NH ₂ .

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Starting Materials: *o*-, *m*- and *p*-Nitrophenyl hydrazones of ethyl pyruvate prepared according to Rydon and Siddappa³ were cyclised by the method of Parmerter and co-workers⁴ to the corresponding 7-, 4-, 6- and 5-nitroindoles.

Preparation of Nitroindole-1-propionitriles (IIa-c): The appropriate nitroindole (0.014 mole) was added to a solution of benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide ('Triton B') (0.6 ml.) and acrylonitrile (1.5 ml.) in dioxan (20 ml.). The resulting mixture was warmed to 80° in an oil bath for 1-2 hrs. and then allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 days. The basic catalyst was neutralised with very dilute acetic acid and the solid nitrile that separated was crystallised from ethanol.

The nitriles thus obtained are described in Table 1.

Preparation of 1-(3-Aminopropyl) aminoindoles (IIIa-c): Nitroindole-1-propionitrile (1 g.) was reduced in methanol (100 ml.) with freshly prepared Raney nickel (0.5 g.) and hydrogen (60 lb/in.²) in a Parr—low pressure hydrogenation apparatus for 6 hrs. The catalyst was filtered off and the filtrate was distilled to remove all methanol, whereby, 1-(3-aminopropyl)aminoindole (0.7 g.) was obtained as a colourless semi-solid mass. This was immediately converted into its dibenzoyl derivative and crystallised from aqueous dioxan.

The dibenzoyl derivatives of 1-(3-aminopropyl) aminoindoles are described in Table 1.

Preparation of Nitroindole-1-propionic acids (IVa-c): The nitrile (1 g.) in aqueous potassium hydroxide (10%, 20 ml.) was heated under reflux for 3 hrs. The resulting solution was cooled and acidified with dilute acetic acid. The precipitated yellow solid was purified by reprecipitating from sodium hydrogen carbonate (10%) and crystallised from aqueous ethanol.

The acids prepared are described in Table 1.

Preparation of 1-(2-cyanoethyl)nitroindole-3-aldehydes (Va-c): Phosphorus oxychloride (1 ml.) was added with stirring to dimethylformamide (1.6 g., 0.022 mole) at 10°–20°. Nitroindole-1-propionitrile (0.005 mole) in dimethylformamide (2 g.) was then slowly added to the above mixture at 20°–30°. After keeping the reaction mixture for one hr. at 45°, it was poured into ice and the clear solution was treated with sodium hydroxide (0.5 g. in 5 ml. water). The mixture was boiled for one minute and allowed to stand. The crystalline material that separated was collected by filtration. The above product was recrystallised from ethanol to get 1-(2-cyanoethyl)-nitroindole-3-aldehyde.

The aldehydes prepared are listed in the Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	m.p. °C	% Found			Molecular formula	% Required		
		C	H	N		C	H	N
IIa	118–19	61.08	4.38	19.22	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	61.41	4.19	19.54
IIb	139–40	61.10	4.28	19.78	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	61.41	4.19	19.54
IIc	145–46	61.23	4.35	19.41	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	61.41	4.19	19.54
dibenzoyl derivative of								
IIIa	153–55	—	—	10.45	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	—	—	10.58
dibenzoyl derivative of								
IIIb	130–32	—	—	10.71	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	—	—	10.58
dibenzoyl derivative of								
IIIc	182–84	—	—	10.67	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	—	—	10.58
IVa	151–53	56.30	4.38	12.17	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	56.41	4.27	11.97
IVb	129–30	56.20	4.40	12.06	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	56.41	4.27	11.97
IVc	182–83	56.53	4.47	12.25	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	56.41	4.27	11.97
Va	133–35	—	—	17.43	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	—	—	17.28
Vb	222–23	—	—	17.51	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	—	—	17.28
Vc	244–46	—	—	17.36	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	—	—	17.28

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